

ISic4420

Epitaph for Aristokrates

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

plinth

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Metcalfe 2016 visited site

Last Change

2020-05-28 - Jonathan Prag created the file from template, publications, and photographs

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

Tomb 105 of the necropolis in contrada Cardusa , where it remains in situ

Coordinates

38.065190, 15.114380

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Tripi, Necropoli di Abakainon

Physical Description

Plinth (support for a stele) with moulding around the top and bottom. The upper moulding of the plinth is partly lost, but the inscribed face is almost completely intact (although lightly scored across the surface). The plinth is the right one of a pair mounted on a single base, classified as an epitombion of type C.

Dimensions

Height 31 cm

Width 51.5 cm

Depth 52.5 cm

Layout

Two lines of Greek letters rather irregularly laid out (not strictly observing the horizontal) and not strictly centred; the single word is split across two lines

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Somewhat irregular plainly cut, widely spaced letters, poorly laid out. Alpha is broad with straight bar; rho has closed eye, somewhat angular in the first instance, more curved in the second; sigma has horizontal top and bottom strokes, angular mid-strokes, very crudely done in the first instance; omicron is very small and mid-line; kappa has short equal bars joined to the vertical; epsilon has shorter middle bar.

Letter heights:

Line 1-2: 49 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: Not recorded mm

Text

1. Ἀριστοκρά

2. τεος

Apparatus

text as per Sofia 2018

Translation (en)

(tomb) of Aristokrates

Commentary

The epitaph consists of a single name in the genitive, as with the majority of the epitaphs attested from this necropolis. This epitaph is one of a pair, the second (ISic4419 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4419>]) commemorating Aristarchos. The evidence of ISic4415 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4415>] / ISic4416 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4416>] and of ISic4417 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4417>] / ISic4418 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4418>] suggests that the two individuals were related (brothers?). The name Ἀριστοκράτεος [http://classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/lgpn_search.cgi?name=%E1%BC%88%CF%81%CE%B9%CF%83%CF%84%CE%BF%CE%BA%CF%81%CE%AC%CF%84%CE%B7%CF%82] is widely attested, including c.11 attestations in Sicily (all from the eastern half of the island; to the 10 currently in LGPN, add ISic3387 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3387>] from Syracuse). Both this epitaph and its partner are notable for the relatively crude layout and formation of the letters (in this case, the letters are significantly larger than in ISic4419, with the result that the name does not fit on a single line).

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Sofia, G. 2018. Nuove iscrizioni funerarie dalla necropoli di Abakainon. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. 206: 103-112. At 108 no.10 and fig.11

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